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RAKHMATULLAEVA Asalkhon Gayratovna*The National Institute of Arts and Design**named after Kamoliddin Behzod**Doctor of Philosophy in Art studies (PhD)*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15498252>**“INTERPRETATION OF DIVINE AND MYSTICAL IDEAS
IN MINIATURES OF THE HERAT SCHOOL”
(Epic “Khayrat ul-abror”)****ANNOTATION**

The article pays special attention to religious themes and plots in miniatures created by artists of the medieval Herat school for the epic poem of Alisher Navai “Khayrat ul-abror”.

The first image in the prologue of the poem was created by Kamoliddin Behzod and is dedicated to the Prophet. It is in this part that much attention is paid to the images of the Prophet and angels. In addition, the image of such figures as sheikhs, sages and saints help to strengthen the ideas of Sufism in miniatures.

Keywords: Alisher Navai, Herat school, poem “Khayrat ul-abror”, Kamoliddin Behzod, image of the Prophet, image of angels, miniature.

**“ИЛОҲИЙ ВА МИСТИК ҒОЯЛАРНИ ТАЛҚИН ҚИЛИШ
ҲИРОТ МАКТАБИНИНГ МИНИАТЮРАЛАРИДА”
(“Хайрат ул-аброр” достони)****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Мақолада Алишер Навоийнинг “Хайрат ул-аброр” достонига ўрта аср Ҳирот мактаби ижодкорлари томонидан ишланган миниатюралардаги диний мавзу ва сюжетларга алоҳида эътибор қаратилган.

Достон муқаддимасидаги илк расм Камолиддин Беҳзод томонидан яратилган, Пайғамбар наътига бағишланган. Айнан наът қисмида Пайғамбар ва фаришталарнинг тасвирларига алоҳида эътибор қаратилган. Шунингдек, шайхлар, донишманд ва авлиёлар каби образларнинг тасвирланиши миниатюралардаги тасаввуф ғояларининг ошишига хизмат қилади.

Калит сўзлар: Алишер Навоий, Ҳирот мактаби, “Хайрат ул-аброр” достони, Камолиддин Беҳзод, Пайғамбар тасвири, фаришталар тасвири, миниатюра.

**“ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ БОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ И МИСТИЧЕСКИХ ИДЕЙ
В МИНИАТЮРАХ ГЕРАТСКОЙ ШКОЛЫ”
(Эпос “Хайрат уль-аброр”)****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В статье особое внимание уделено религиозным темам и сюжетам в миниатюрах, созданных художниками средневековой гератской школы к эпической поэме Алишера Наваи «Хайрат ул-аброр».

Первое изображение в прологе поэмы создана Камолиддином Бехзодом и посвящена Пророку. Именно в этой части большое внимание уделяется изображениям Пророка и ангелов. Кроме того, изображение таких фигур, как шейхи, мудрецы и святые, способствует усилению идей суфизма в миниатюрах.

Ключевые слова: Алишер Наваи, гератская школа, поэма «Хайрат ул-аброр», Камолиддин Бехзод, изображение Пророка, изображение ангелов, миниатюра.

The traditions of Herat literature and epic manuscripts later influenced cultural centers such as Bukhara, Isfahan, Tabriz, and Agra, both with and through the manuscripts of the poet's works, and also served as the basis for the creation of new manuscripts as a creative competition. In general, the influence of the poet's works on the cultural life, painting, calligraphy, and the development of the history of literature in Herat, Bukhara, Tabriz, Isfahan, and Agra during the XVth and XVIth centuries is very great. The results of this can be seen especially clearly in painting.

The epic poem "Khayrat ul-abror". Alisher Navoi admitted that since childhood he had dreamed of creating the epic poem "Khamasa" not in Persian, like Nizami Ganjavi and Amir Khusraw Dehlavi, but in his native language, the Turkic-Uzbek language. He began to realize this noble intention in 888/1483.

The poet entered into a creative competition with his teachers, first of all, thoroughly studying their epics and the history related to the content of the epics, and as a result of this, he created his works. Epics are not just artistic compositions, but also serve as a means for the poet to express his attitude to events related to the fate of his people and all peoples [11, P.56].

Although the epic poem "Khayrat ul-abror" [1] fully adheres to the traditions of its predecessors, it is distinguished by its ability to adapt to the new era, to absorb the spirit of the new era, and to reveal new facets of the characters of new heroes or previous heroes. It depicts the Prophet and his companions, as well as Hatam Tai, Nizami Ganjavi, Amir Khusraw Dehlavi, Ibrahim Adham, Rabiyyai Adaviya, Khoja Muhammad Porso, Khoja Abu Nasr, Abdurahman Jami, and the kings Iskandar Zulkarnayn, Anushirvan, Bahram, as well as Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Sultan Husayn Mirzo, Prince Bediuzzaman Mirzo, and others. This was a remarkable event and novelty in the history of the East.

If we talk about the illustrations used in the epic poem "Khayrat ul-abror", the first illustration in the preface to the epic was created by Kamoliddin Behzod and is dedicated to the Prophet's poem. It depicts the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) and his four companions on the mosque's steps, which he used for a manuscript he created for Prince Bediuzzaman [2].

The mosque's steps and pulpit are decorated with exquisitely carved scrolls in Suls script, quoting verses and hadiths. The Prophet and his companions are depicted in the traditions of Herat's XVth century art, in particular, in the depictions in Khaydar al-Khwarizmi's "Mi'rajname". As in life, in the text, and in the painting, the Prophet's figure is singled out, and a golden circle of fire, the symbol of prophethood, is depicted on his head. Sh. M. Shukurov, who has studied the depiction of the Prophet in miniatures, paid great attention to the fact that her face is depicted under a veil in her last paintings, as her personality is deified, and he searches for the reasons for this. [14, P.98]

The fact that the miniature depicts the Prophet's face can be explained by the fact that the Holy Quran states that Prophets are also ordinary people, and that in many Hadiths, our Prophet called people to good behavior, saying, "I am also a human being, a human being like you." This is probably why the most complete and best of the poet's epics about the noble ones who serve as role models for others seem to depict the Prophet and his companions.

Another striking feature of the painting is that Hazrat Ali is depicted writing down the words of the Prophet. This is not without reason. Calligraphers, including Sultan Ali Mashhadi, in his treatise on "Husnihat", also praise Hazrat Ali as a calligrapher and one of the inventors of calligraphy [14, P.37].

In general, it should be said that the tradition of depicting the personalities of the prophets as ordinary people, resembling them or close to them, continued in the paintings created later by Kamal al-Din Behzad in the Herat miniature school [13, P.74].

However, it cannot be said that this tradition continued everywhere.

In the miniature on the theme of “The Shah’s conversation with the Imam in the Bath” [3] the image is not just a scene in the bath, but a conversation between the Khorezm Shah Sultan Muhammad and Imam Fakhr Razi.

Fakhr Razi was a famous scholar in Khorezm who contributed to the development of his country with his knowledge and intellect. In addition to the Khorezm Shah Sultan Muhammad, people from all over the world came to visit him. One day, the Shah met Fakhr Razi in the bath and asked him: “What will happen to a person on the Day of Judgment?” The wise man said: “On that day, both the king and the poor will be naked, as they are now. If the king and his nobles throw off their clothes when entering that world, then scholars like me will enter it with the good deeds they have achieved.”

“The Shah’s conversation with the Imam in the Bath”. 1492. Herat.

The miniature belongs to the Herat school, but Indian artists painted the faces of the heroes and gave them a national character. This miniature is characterized by the expressive construction, the architectural interpretation decorated with the colorful tone characteristic of Herat, the richness of color and other aspects of the style.

In the center of the work, the king and the sage are depicted talking among the people who came to the bath. On the inner stage of the blue marble bath, on the left, the king is depicted talking to his interlocutor. Behind him are two nobles.

On both sides of the building’s carved wall, two figures of angels are depicted, interspersed with images of plants. They seem to be listening to a conversation about the afterlife and watching the heroes. The garden visible behind the building represents the worries of this world and our good deeds floating around us like clouds. On the right, people who are about to enter the bathhouse through the doorway give the impression that they are standing at the entrance to that world and are taking off their clothes outside. Each object, image, and characters in the miniature reflects the content of the conversation between the main characters.

Another work by the great artist Kamoliddin Behzod, entitled “Khoja Abdullah Ansari in conversation with Dervishes” [4] depicts the hero as a guide of the perfect in faith, a man of character, who was considered the qibla not only by the people of Herat, but also by the entire universe. “My work consists in obedience and submission to the commands of God!” he would say. At first glance, the miniature seems to depict a simple conversation between Khoja Abdullah Ansari in the garden. The hero of the work is depicted sitting on a carpet with four dervishes, talking to the two dervishes sitting to his left, slightly bowing his head. On its back is a building decorated with beautiful girih and Islamic patterns in the Herat style, and on the right side is a depiction of mountains skillfully crafted by the artist.

“Khoja Abdullah Ansari in conversation with Dervishes”. 1485. Herat.

If looking closely at the image of the mountains, can see that a cunning fox chases a mountain goat to the top. The poor animal is unable to even move. According to some sources, the fox, sensing the appetizing smells coming from the house, looks for a way into the house through the chimney, since the doors and windows are closed. Since the house has a high roof, it chases the mountain goat to the very top of the mountain, jumps over it, and tries to enter the place where the smoke is coming from.

The main goal of a creative person who wanted to rise to the top of art was to be accepted by society. To do this, society had to get acquainted with his works and recognize him as an artist who creates true works of art. In the Middle Ages, before works were presented to the public, it was necessary to obtain the permission of the great Sheikh. As a form of spiritual permission, a group of critics carefully analyzed the created work and looked for forbidden ideas in it.

The artist is forced to behave like a fox in order to avoid the critics and convey his ideas. Shaikh asks the critics what are the mistakes in the work. They say they have no objections to the community. The Sheikh unwittingly allows the work to pass without understanding the true purpose and symbolic expression depicted by the artist. According to the content of the miniature, only the works created based on the mystical religious ideas of that time were approved by the group of critics headed by the Sheikh and brought to the public's attention. You can understand that Kamoliddin Behzod was a great philosopher and scientist just by the image above.

Similar philosophical and mystical ideas to the works reviewed are also evident in a number of other miniatures used in the manuscript of the epic poem “Khayrat ul-abror”. Among them, we can single out works on the themes of “Anushirvan with the Queen in the palace” [5], “The presentation of Sheikh Iraqi to the crowd” [6] (four miniatures from the Bodlean manuscript were used for the epic poem), “Sheikh Iraqi receiving the Syrian Ruler” [7], “Sheikh Iraqi meeting with the Prince” [8], as well as illustrations called “Battlefield” [9] and “Battle” [10], which are characteristic of the Maverannakhr miniature school.

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